

EFFECTS OF PRESS MOLDING CONDITIONS ON IMPREGNATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER FABRIC/PA6 FILM COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

For the reduction of CO₂ emission to restrain the global warming, improving the fuel consumption efficiency by reducing the vehicle's weight is one of the promising ways. In the developments of applying light weight carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) to vehicle parts, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) is more attractive for the mass productivity and recyclability than thermoset CFRP. Especially, CFRTP consisting of continuous fibers has high strength, and it has the potential to be applied to the structural parts [1,2].

There are several ways of manufacturing CFRTP consisting of continuous fibers. The film stacking method, which consists of stacking thermoplastic film and carbon fiber fabric alternatively and then pressing them into composite with heat and pressure by press machine, is one of the notable ways to produce CFRTP plate. The impregnation process of thermoplastic resin, which has high melt viscosity, into carbon fiber bundles gains importance because the impregnation quality has a great influence on the physical property of the composite [3]. Therefore, in the technology of mass production of CFRTP by press machine using heat and pressure, it is important to investigate the relationship among the press molding conditions especially about the heat and pressure, the physical property, and impregnation quality of the composite. There have been a number of studies about the press molding conditions using several kinds of fibers and resins so far [4,5,6,7].

In Ishikawa Carbon Fiber Cluster (ICFC), Japan, we are aiming to build a broad range of production foundation of CFRTP in Ishikawa. We are developing CFRTP technology and advancing the commercialization. Development of CFRTP

stampable sheet is one of the aims of our development activities. That is the laminate sheet consisting of thermoplastic resin and carbon fiber fabric, in which the resin is impregnated into continuous carbon fiber bundles. As it is known, various kinds of parts can be produced from the stampable sheet by stamp forming with a short cycle time. We think that the stampable CFRTP sheet can be applied to the industrial use such as vehicles, which need low cost production and short cycle time. One of the important subjects about the manufacturing of stampable sheet is to establish low cost production technology. Now, we anticipate that the production cost could be lowered by reducing the processing pressure and shortening the processing time.

In this study, we used polyamide 6 (PA6) as thermoplastic resin because of their strength and high heat resistance. In order to obtain the fundamental data about the processing conditions, we investigated the relationship among the press molding conditions of PA6 / carbon fiber plain woven fabric, the impregnation quality, and physical property of composite. We used the film stacking method and the heat-and-cool system, which consists of heating and cooling the mold during the process.

2 Experimentals

2.1 Materials

Carbon fiber plain woven fabric (T700SC-12k, Toray Co., Ltd.), and PA6 film (Amilan, thickness: 100 μ m, Toray Co., Ltd.) were used in this study. Generally, sizing agent is applied to the commercialized carbon fibers. In advance, we heated the carbon fiber fabrics at 400°C to remove

the sizing agent, which has been reported to prevent the impregnation of resin into carbon fiber bundles [8,9].

2.2 Molding process

9 layers of PA6 films and 8 layers of carbon fiber plain woven fabrics were piled up alternately. The stacking sequence was $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$. Stacked materials were pressed by a hydraulic press machine with a flat mold of 100 mm x 100 mm. The press machine has the system to heat and cool the mold. In the preheating process, materials were heated for 10 minutes to melt the resin without pressure. After preheating process, materials were pressed by certain pressure for certain time, and then cooled down to less than 80°C at the rate of about 70°C/min. Finally, the laminate was taken out from the mold. The typical molding process diagram used in this study is shown in Fig. 1. Preheating time is fixed, and molding temperature, molding time and molding pressure were varied to investigate the relationship among the press molding conditions, the impregnation quality and physical property of composite. The molding time means the time in which the molding pressure is kept at the molding temperature, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Typical press molding process diagram

2.3 Thermal properties of PA6 film

First, we measured the melt viscosity of PA6 film with Melt Indexer (L990-E14708, Tateyama Kagaku Industry Co., Ltd.). The measurement temperatures were 230°C and 250°C. We obtained the average value of 5 time measurements and evaluated melt volume rate (MVR).

Second, we measured the melting point and crystallization temperature of PA6 film using DSC

(EXSTAR DSC7200, SII Nano Technology Co., Ltd). The temperature was raised up from -20°C to 280°C, and then cooled down from 280°C to -20°C. From the DSC curve, we evaluated the melting point and the crystallization temperature.

Third, we measured the thermal degradation temperature of PA6, using TG/DTA (EXSTAR TG/DTA7300, SII Nano Technology Co., Ltd). The temperature was raised up from room temperature to 400°C at the rate of 10°C/min under the air atmosphere. From the TG curve, we evaluated the starting temperature of thermal degradation of PA6.

2.4 Evaluation of composites

In order to investigate the impregnation quality of composite, we measured the void content calculated from the composite density and the volume fraction of carbon fibers in the composite. At first, we measured the composite density by water replacement method. And we burned out the resin of the composite using a gas burner, and calculated the volume fraction of carbon fibers (V_f) from equations (1) and (2).

$$W_f = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$V_f = \frac{W_f \times \rho_c}{\rho_f} \quad (2)$$

Where W_f is the weight fraction of carbon fibers, m_0 is the weight of the composite, m_1 is the weight of the composite after burned out by a gas burner, ρ_c is the composite density, ρ_f is the carbon fiber density which was 1.8 g/cm³ based on the catalog data.

Then, we calculated the apparent void content V_v from equations (3), (4).

$$V_r = \frac{(100 - W_f) \times \rho_c}{\rho_r} \quad (3)$$

$$V_v = 100 - (V_f + V_r) \quad (4)$$

Where V_r is the volume fraction of resin, ρ_r is the resin density which was 1.14g/cm³. In order to confirm the impregnation quality in the visual observation, we cut the cross-section of the composites using a diamond cutter, and observed the polished cross sections by optical microscopy.

Finally, we performed three-point flexure test using a universal testing machine (100kNPlus, Shimazu Co., Ltd.). The specimens were cut out from the composites using a diamond cutter. Geometry of specimen was 15 mm in width and 100 mm in length. Tests were performed with 80 mm span length and 5 mm/min test speed according to JIS K 7074[10].

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Thermal properties of PA6 film

The MVR result of PA6 film is shown in Table 1. As the temperature became higher, the melt viscosity decreased. It was supposed that lower melting viscosity eases the impregnation of resin into carbon fiber bundles. Therefore, we investigated the thermal properties of PA6 film in detail in order to obtain the range of molding temperature.

Table 1 MVR result of PA6 film

Temperature / °C	MVR/ cm ³ /10min
230°C	10.4
250°C	17.7

The DSC curve of PA6 film is shown in Fig. 2. The melting point was 220°C in the heating process, and the crystallization temperature was 194°C in the cooling process. The TG curve of PA6 film is shown in Fig. 3. In the air atmosphere, the weight began to decrease at about 310°C and the thermal degradation began.

Accordingly, the molding temperature should be above 220°C and should not exceed 310°C. In the cooling process, the materials should be cooled down to under 150°C, which is the completion time of crystallization of the resin. In this study, the materials were cooled down to 80°C after molding.

Fig. 2 DSC result of PA6 film

Fig. 3 TG curve of PA6 film under air atmosphere

3.2 Influence of molding temperature

In order to investigate the influence of the molding temperature on the composites, we performed the press molding tests with various molding temperature. We selected the temperature range from 230°C, which is slightly above the melting point, to 340°C, which is slightly above the degradation starting temperature, according to the PA6 thermal properties based on Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The molding pressure was fixed at 10MPa and the molding time was fixed for 10min.

Figure 4 shows the relationship between the molding temperature and the void content of composite. Although the void contents were less than 2% at the temperature from 230 to 310°C, it became above 5% at 320°C. Figure 5 shows the cross sectional photograph of the composites. In the case of 230°C, the resin was impregnated enough into carbon fiber bundles. However, in the case of 340°C, the voids can be observed clearly among the carbon fibers which gather closely and the resin seemed to disappear to some extent. Because PA6

began the thermal degradation above 310°C, the resin vaporization might induce these voids.

Fig. 4 Relationship between molding temperature and void content of composites

Fig.5 Cross-sectional photograph of composites (molding pressure: 10MPa, molding time: 10min) ((a): 230°C (V_v 1%), (b): 340°C (V_v 11%)) (white area: weft and warp carbon fibers, grey area: resin, black area: voids)

Figures 6 and 7 show the relationship between the molding temperature and the flexural strength, and between the molding temperature and the flexural modulus, respectively. At the temperature from 230 to 310°C, the flexural strengths were about 750MPa. However, the strength began to decrease rapidly at 320°C. Comparing with the result in Fig.4, this temperature corresponds to that at which the strength began to decrease. It was reported that the flexural strength of CFRTP had a good correlation to the impregnation quality, that is, as the impregnation quality became better, the flexural strength improved [11]. On the other hand, the flexural modulus was almost constant at the range from 230°C to 290°C, but slightly increased at over 310°C. As shown in Fig. 8, the composite thickness became thinner and V_f became higher at over 310°C. It could be one of the reasons that the apparent modulus increased.

Fig. 6 Relationship between molding temperature and flexural strength of composites

Fig. 7 Relationship between molding temperature and flexural modulus of composites

Fig. 8 Relationship between molding temperature and the V_f and thickness of composites

3.3 Influence of molding time

We investigated the relationship among the molding time, the impregnation quality and the flexural property of composite. We selected 230°C, 270°C and 310°C as the molding temperature and varied the molding time from 2.5min to 10min. The molding pressure was fixed at 10MPa.

Figure 9 shows the relationship between the molding time and the void content of composite. At the molding temperature of 230°C and 270°C, the void content decreased with increase of the molding time. Especially at 230°C, this tendency was remarkable. It is thought that the impregnation quality was improved with increase of the molding time. In contrast, the void content for the molding time of 2.5min at 310°C was lower than those with 10min at both 230°C and 270°C. This result suggests that the melt viscosity at 310°C was low enough and the resin could be impregnated into carbon fiber bundles even for the molding time of 2.5min. However, the void content increased at 310°C with increase of the molding time. Because the thermal degradation began at 310°C, it is thought that the resin degradation progressed and the void content increased with increase of the molding time. Fig. 10 shows the cross sectional photographs of composite. Although the resin was impregnated enough at 310°C for 2.5min, insufficient impregnation and much voids were observed at 230°C.

Fig. 9 Relationship between molding time and void content of composites

Fig. 10 Cross-sectional photograph of composites (molding pressure: 10MPa, molding time: 2.5min) ((a): 230°C (V_v 3%), (b): 310°C (V_v 1%)), (white area: weft and warp carbon fibers, grey area: resin, black area: voids)

Figure 11 shows the relationship between the molding time and the flexural strength of composite. At 230 and 270°C, the flexural strength tended to increase with the molding time, and reached about 760MPa for 10min of molding time. On the other hand, at 310°C, the flexural strength reached 770MPa even for 2.5min, and then the strength rather decreased with increase of molding time. This tendency corresponds to those of the void content. Figure 12 shows the relationship between the molding time and the flexural modulus of composite. Flexural moduli were almost constant regardless of the molding time at any molding temperature. The high values in 10 min of the molding time were supposedly influenced by increase of V_f as mentioned above.

Fig. 11 Relationship between molding time and flexural strength of composites

Fig. 12 Relationship between molding time and flexural modulus of composites

3.4 Influence of molding pressure

We found that enough impregnation quality and strength could be obtained at both 270°C and 310°C even for 2.5min of the molding time. Here, we evaluated the molding pressure varied from 2.5MPa to 10MPa for 2.5min at 270°C and 310°C.

Figure 13 shows the relationship between the molding pressure and the void content of composite. Though the pressure decreased, the void was constantly about 2% in the case of 310°C. On the other hand, void content increased to 4% in the case of 270°C. The resin viscosity at 270°C was higher than that at 310°C. Therefore, it was supposed that when the molding pressure decreased the influence of temperature became predominant and induced the difference in the impregnation quality. Figure 14 shows the cross sectional photographs of composite. Although the resin was impregnated enough in the case of 310°C, insufficient impregnation and the voids were observed in the case of 270°C. The voids were scattered particularly in the middle of fiber bundles, which could mean that the resin impregnation started outside the fiber bundle and then proceeded into the center area.

Fig. 13 Relationship between molding pressure and void content of composites

Fig. 14 Cross-sectional photograph of composites (molding pressure: 2.5MPa, molding time: 2.5min) ((a): 270°C (V_v 4%), (b): 310°C (V_v 2%)) (white area: weft and warp carbon fibers, grey area: resin, black area: voids)

Figure 15 shows the relationship between the molding pressure and the flexural strength of composite. In the pressure range adopted in our study, the strength decreased with decrease of the molding pressure in the case of 270°C. On the other hand, the strength was constantly about 750MPa in the case of 310°C. This tendency corresponds to the results of the void contents. The flexural modulus was constant regardless of the pressure, as shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 15 Relationship between molding pressure and flexural strength of composites

Fig. 16 Relationship between molding pressure and flexural modulus of composites

4 Conclusions

One of the important technical subjects about the manufacturing of stampable sheet is to establish low cost production technology. We investigated the relationship among the press molding conditions of PA6 / carbon fiber plain woven fabric, the impregnation quality, and physical property of composite and optimize the press molding conditions with low pressure and short cycle time. We obtained the following results.

Based on the thermal properties of PA6 film, the molding temperature should be in the range from 220°C to 310°C.

At the molding temperature of 320°C and over, the void content became higher due to the thermal degradation of resin and the flexural strength decreased remarkably by the influence of the voids.

The resin viscosity at 310°C was lower and could be impregnated to carbon fiber bundles enough even

with shorter time than at lower temperature. The resin thermal degradation began at 310°C, however, it was thought that it could be restricted by shortening the molding time.

We found that the enough impregnation quality and strength could be obtained at 310°C even with the low molding pressure such as 2.5MPa and also for the low molding time such as 2.5min, different from the case of the lower temperature such as 270°C. This result suggests that the temperature of 310°C should be the most suitable for the process with low pressure and short cycle time. It is interesting from the industrial point of view because our results showed the possibility for the low cost production of the stampable sheet.

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